

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE

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Annotation: *Comparative Literature focuses on the study of literature from different cultures, nations, and genres, and explores relationships between literature and other forms of cultural expression. Sometimes when we have so much material, we don't know what to compare it with. There are many factors in the process of comparative analysis and its results are affected. In addition, this article provides theoretical foundations that we should take into account in order to compare two different literatures.*

Key words: *Comparative literature, comparative analysis, effects of external conditions, literary events, literary phenomena, theoretical laws of literature.*

Any comparative study reveals the commonalities and peculiarities of literary events. This is the basis for the development of general theoretical laws of literature.

Comparative analysis is different from simple analysis. Traditional analysis consists of objects, which are their constituents. That fact must be taken into account. «In addition to these actions, comparative analysis also focuses on comparing the components of the objects of analysis.

First of all, the researcher must choose the objects of comparison correctly. Because the state of existence of the objects of comparison creates these stages.

Firstly, it is impossible to compare, identify similarities and differences of events without comparing their internal properties and internal parameters. Their main ones are the content, essence, qualities of the objects being compared. Therefore, identifying similarities and differences between the content, nature, and qualities of events is the first step in the comparison process.

Second, we know that the internal properties of events, that is, their content, essence, and quality, are manifested in a specific way in the environment. Therefore, it is necessary to study the internal properties of the objects of comparison, the similarities and differences in the level of their manifestation in the environment. This is the next stage of the comparative analysis.

Third, not only do the objects being compared affect the environment, but the environment also affects them. This involves comparing the effects of external conditions on the objects of analysis. In this way, the third direction is naturally determined at the stage of comparison of events. Its essence is to identify similarities and differences in the impact of the environment on the objects of comparative analysis.

Fourth, there is a reason for every event, including a literary one. Of course, they should be taken into account when comparing. Many needs play a role in the origin, existence, development, and functioning of each event and some of them are priorities. This is what we often call the motive in the literature. So, before we do a comparative analysis of what we need, we also need to compare the needs and wants that created it. This helps us to identify similarities and differences due to the existence of objects being compared. To do this, we need to perform a comparative analysis based on the algorithm of necessity (motive) - object - essence (result).

Hence, comparing needs (motives) is an important step in object analysis because nothing happens without need and necessity. After all, in Alisher Navoi's *Lison ut-tayr*, the first of the seven valleys chosen to reach the original destination was exactly what was required

Sometimes when we have so much material, we don't know what to compare it with. As you know, there are many factors in the process of comparative analysis and its results are affected. With all of this in mind, the following typical situations can be compared:

The first situation. Comparison of literary events in one place and time. This comparison process has its own characteristics. First, the spatial unity of the objects being compared, the generality of the environment, removes from the agenda the study of how it affects these properties. The general space and time, on the other hand, indicate that the environment of the objects of comparison is the same, and that the environment has essentially the same effect on them. This leads to a slight "simplification" of the comparative analysis. Second, the existence of comparable phenomena in one space and one time, of course, allows us to speak of their historical unity. For example, a comparative study of the works of Utkir Hoshimov and Tahir Malik reveals the general and specific aspects of writers who lived and worked in the same space and time.

The second situation. It is a space, but a comparison of literary events from different eras. A second situation arises when it is necessary to compare literary events that exist, exist, or may exist in a particular setting, in the same environment,

in the same space, but at different times. At the same time, it is difficult to compare events that occur at different times but in very similar situations. Usually, certain problems, difficulties, puzzles occur here.

They often try to compare events in the same place, for example, in a country, by denying the time factor.

This is incorrect. For example, poets who have lived and worked in the same place but at different times: Muqimi and Muhammad Yusuf's views on youth or youth will, of course, be judged by time. In other words, even if the objects being compared exist in the same environment, it must be taken into account that time has a different effect on the nature of the problem at different stages of its development. Even if the circumstances in which the events took place (country, place) have not changed radically, the objects of comparison may have changed during this time.

The third situation. Compare objects that exist at the same time but in different places. For example, today there is a novel of the same name "Revenge" by Uzbek writer Nasir Zahid and American writer Victoria Schwab, who live and work at the same time, but in different places. When comparing the motives of revenge in both novels, it is important to take into account the effect of the environment on the objects of comparison. This process requires special attention from the researcher. Because in the process of comparative analysis it is necessary to take into account the influence of conditions and causes on the objects being compared.

The fourth situation. The process of comparing literary phenomena of different spaces and times. It compares different environments, spaces, and literary events of different eras. This situation is considered to be the most complex for the methodology and methodology of comparative analysis. For example, in order to study the interpretation of enlightenment in the works of Shakespeare and Alisher Navoi, or in the works of Abdullah Qahhor and Jack London, it is necessary to consider the following:

First, it is necessary to understand the nature of the events being compared. Second, as far as possible, the previous conditions and environments in which the objects of comparative analysis exist a deeper study is needed to reveal their influence on the worldview of Shakespeare and Navoi or Abdullah Qahhor and Jack London. Because in order to find out what unites the works of writers who have lived and worked in different times and places, other than fame, it is necessary to reveal many literary events.

Due to the spatial and temporal characteristics of the objects of comparison, the analyst faces many challenges. But if the characteristics of the situations that

arise in the course of the development of comparable literary phenomena are taken into account, they can be solved. If the researchers conducting the comparative analysis have a methodology and methodology for comparing different, conflicting events, the comparison result will be more effective.

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